

CHAPTER-I

INTRODUCTION

“Tourism education is not simply about vocationalism”

Airey (2004, p.11).

Tourism has reached all the countries across the globe; it brings income generation, foreign exchange earnings and employment creation. As per the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) tourism has proved itself solely ‘as a solution where other industries have failed’ and as ‘a force for good’ i.e. community development, environment conservation, alternate to traditional/non environment friendly practices, product development and women empowerment. Consequently, tourism through economic development is also reaching the door steps of the vulnerable and remote parts of the globe. Tourism generates thousands of jobs in various sectors of business. Specifically with regard to tourism industry, career avenues can be divided into five areas i.e. accommodation, food and beverage services, recreation and entertainment, transportation and travel services (British Columbia Jobs, 2015). The government of India has initiated a threshold step towards 5 trillion economy by 2025 and marked tourism as a ‘champion’ to achieve this towering goal (Economic Times, 2019a). The government has planned to extract soft power of tourism as it was not been acted upon before. There is a futuristic plan to grow tourism by five times through public-private partnership (PPP). This partnership will help to identify and to develop 20 tourism destinations across the country (Economic times, 2019b). India’s emergence as a global power has grown tourism industry that generates revenue, in form of different currencies, not only for government but also for the natives where they directly get benefitted by the visitors across the world. Twenty first century is known for globalization where interconnectedness of foreign cultures is observed as a new paradigm shift of socio-economic and cultural elevations. Apart from cultural exchange, tourism instigates human mind to explore the specialities and wonderfulness of various landmasses and variations in biological, geographical and cultural set up into it. It is paramount to analyse the globally emerging demand of tourism and to find ways to attract visitors and tourists. In present scenario of globalisation, there is a dire need for

transformation in education. Understanding and entangling of transformed education and multifaceted globalisation can delineate tourism education for worldwide change. Suarez-Orozco and Qin-Hilliard (2004) have mentioned globalisation is multifaceted and discussed that “Globalisation will continue to be a powerful vector of worldwide change. We need better understanding of how education will be transformed by globalisation and how it, in turn, can shape and manage the course of courses of globalisation. We need better theoretical understanding of globalisation’s multiple faces-economic, demographic, social and cultural. We need more dialogue among scholars, practitioners, and policy makers” (p. 25). Tourism is a leading global industry having a significant role in the world’s production, trade, employment, and investment. It provides important source of foreign exchange and foreign direct investment. Tourism also seeks cultural and environmental conservation, and social wellbeing where reinforcement is given to tourism education and governance. All forms of tourism can contribute towards the development of local communities through tourism education. Tourism can have both positive and negative impacts, depending on how it is planned, developed, managed and brought under government policies its effect can felt. But it can be monitored through tourism education and minimum required governance of the destination. Tourism education and governance are the only tool which can enable conditions which are required for transforming tourism to contribute to socio-economic developments within carrying capacities of destination. Year 2019 witnessed strong growth in row for the global Travel and Tourism sector reinforcing its role as a driver of economic growth and job creation (WTTC, 2020) but Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) hit the global tourism industry at worst (United Nations World Tourism Organisation, 2020).

1.1 Benefits of Tourism

According to Smith (1989), the terms ‘tourism’ and ‘tourists’ were commonly used at the beginning of the 19th century and higher level studies about the tourism are the new. During the 1940s, the formal study of tourism was started in North America and led to the tourism knowledge development during 1980s (Koh, 1994). According to Sheldon et al (2011), “Tourism is a hallmark activity of the postmodern world” (p.3). Tourism is shaping the world as well as the human communities. While it can be asserted that education institution are shaping the human resource across the globe.

Integration of tourism activities with tourism education or vice versa can shape the world and society as per desires. According to Urry (2000), Tourism is an important component of modern life as well central part of the society. Tourism is a highly lucrative industry for many economies of the nations. But importance of tourism is unrecognized in the academic arena. Moreover, nature of tourism is changing because of postmodernism. The Travel and Tourism industry is used as a tool by governments across the globe to generate prosperity. Tourism and travel experiences are a major contributor to expanding global awareness and consciousness, which is necessary to achieve sustainable development in an integrated and rapid shrinking world. It is creating jobs which particularly support women, youth and other, often marginalised groups of society (WTTC, 2019). Moreover as per the survey by Hiring Intent Survey (2019), tourism industry has positive trends towards gender equality at workplace (24%) and gender diversity ratio (25%), these trends are above industry (23%). Tourism is practicing sustainable human development through an instrument for poverty alleviation, environmental regeneration, job creation and advancement of women and other disadvantaged groups. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC, 2019), travel and tourism industry in 2018 has growth rate of 3.9%. This industry earned USD 8.8 trillion and generated 319 million jobs across the globe. For the eighth consecutive year, this was above the growth rate of world Gross Domestic Product (GDP). As per WTTC (2019) Travel and Tourism now accounts for one in five of all new jobs created worldwide and is forecast to contribute 100 million new jobs globally over the next ten years, accounting for 421 million jobs by 2029.

Ward and Shiels (2017) have appealed to the world to integrate tourism into the development agenda either nation or region. The tourism leads to sustainable development growth, social inclusiveness, employment, and poverty reduction; resource efficiency, environmental protection, and climate change; cultural values, diversity, and heritage; and mutual understanding, peace and security. The WTTC is in tourism research for more than 25 years. The Council advocates the tourism and travel industry as one of the world's largest economic sector. The industry creates jobs, drives exports, and generates prosperity across the world (WTTC, 2018). The pioneer research has shown travel and tourism industry accounts for 'one in eleven jobs on the planet', growth in national income and balance of payment in a country (WTTC, 2013), through liberal visa policies adoption across the globe tourism is

bridging the borders instead of supporting protectionism (WTTC, 2017). Tourism is not limited to the basic benefits like foreign exchange sources and other economic functions. The industry has opened up new paradigms of opportunities for world population. Tourism in the modern era opens space not only for the blue planet but also for those who can afford expenses to explore space as well, for example the moon, outer space and the red planet. Tourism is playing a major role in international peace because it fuels the cultural understanding among hosts and tourists. International tourism is playing increasingly a paramount role in the world economy and progressively adapt national policies on priority basis keeping futuristic development at the fore. Tourism is generally a travelling phenomenon which is a wonderful adventure where each and every country, even with political instability, are trying to extract the economic, social and environmental benefits by facilitating those who are travelling. World Economic Forum has mentioned (2017), the paradox of tourism, therefore, lies in the tension between our desire to travel the world, and the need to provide the most benefits with the least harm. Many well intentioned people in the public and private sector are by and large looking for solutions that will provide viable, long-term socio-economic benefits for tourist domains.

1.2 Indian Tourism at a Glance

Travel and tourism is the best partner for governments to generate employment; during last five years one in four new jobs were created by the tourism sector. Travel and tourism economy growth rate has reached 3.5 percent in 2019 as compared to global economic growth of 2.5 percent. In 2019, Travel and Tourism's direct, indirect and induced impact accounted for US\$8.9 trillion contribution to the world's GDP, 10.3% of global GDP, 330 million jobs, 1 in 10 jobs around the world, US\$1.7 trillion visitor exports (6.8% of total exports, 28.3% of global services exports) and US\$948 billion capital investment (4.3% of total investment) (WTTC, 2019). According to Statista(2020) in 2019, 29 million people got direct employment in China's travel and tourism industry. It was 27.5 million with regards to Indian tourism industry. Germany has employed the largest number of employees i.e. 3 million in Europe. The China had a population of 139.27 crore and Indian population is 135.26 crore in 2018 while Germany had just 8.3 crore population in 2019. The Table 1.1 shows the percentage growth of Indian tourism industry (direct) is higher

than global tourism industry growth with respect to national GDP and Global GDP respectively. The percentage share of Indian travel and tourism industry (direct) to the national GDP is steady since 2015 and regularity is also found with regard to global perspective as well. It is contrary to national GDP which is fluctuating whereas direct contribution of national travel and tourism industry is steady.

Table 1.1: Current Status of Tourism

Year	World Economic Growth **	% Share(direct) global ***	% growth of(direct) Global ***	National GDP growth*	(% growth) (Direct) National ***	(% share) (Direct) National ***
2009	-1.68	2.9	3.5	8.5	5.4	3.3
2010	4.30	2.9	2.7	10.3	2.1	3.0
2011	3.13	2.9	5.4	6.6	1.2	2.9
2012	2.51	2.9	2.9	5.5	.8	2.7
2013	2.65	2.9	4.2	6.4	1.0	2.6
2014	2.83	3	3.5	7.4	2.0	2.5
2015	2.81	3.1	5.4	8.2	2.8	2.4
2016	2.48	3.1	4.0	7.1	9.9	2.4
2017	3.12	3.1	4.8	6.7	5.3	2.4
2018	2.97	3.2	4.1	6.1	6.7	2.4
2019	--	3.2	3.5	4.2	4.9	2.4

Source:*countryeconomy.com, **World Bank, ***WTTC

1.3 Genesis of Tourism Education

In Western context, the kick start step towards the establishment of tourism knowledge was taken out by rebellious academicians. The Indian academicians (most of) who started tourism education had more ‘affinity for administrative recognition’ than a zeal or motivation for ‘knowledge creation and knowledge sharing in tourism education and tourism industry’. In majority of the countries the origin of tourism education was in business or polytechnic schools. In the context of the United States of America (USA) tourism education evolved from Home Science discipline i.e.

polytechnics and imbibed by Management Discipline i.e. business school. Indian tourism education programs were infused by 'pure social science faculties' to provide employment. Later, tourism education was adopted by Business Management Departments in different Indian Universities with an aim to diversify the growth of departments through bachelor and master courses (George, 2017). With regard to Indian tourism education, the founding stone of tourism education was laid down in the 1970s with the go ahead of a Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism. It was started by College of Vocational Studies (CVS) in 1972, University of Delhi (Singh and Singh, 2006). This course had an aim to integrate the span between "traditional university education and the changing socio-economic environment" (CVS, 2016). Later the tourism education programs were initiated by Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna University (HNBGU), Uttarakhand offering a Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism and Pilgrimage Studies under Department of Tourism in 1976 (HNBGU, 2013). Later, this was rechristened as Centre for Mountain Tourism and Hospitality Studies (CMTHS) in 2001. If CVS is considered as a prime mover of tourism education in India, the tourism education has appeared to have enter the 5th decade. The lifelong creativity, productivity and satisfaction among produced tourism graduates are the prime motto of CMTHS, HNBGU.

The life cycle of tourism education is definitely not at same stages across the globe and varies from country to country (Ladkin, 2014). These stages vary from introductory stage to 'declined stage' on the bases of 'popularity' and 'degree of disciplination'. In USA, United Kingdom (UK) and Australian tourism education is at declined stage or stagnation while Indian tourism education is at 'introductory stage' (George, 2017). The Australian institute has adopted internationalization (multinational campuses and overseas promotion) of tourism education, while in USA and UK Universities had either repositioned the tourism programs or phase out the institutes. In West, there are dedicated Universities on tourism studies. At the beginning tourism education started for skill development (knowledge utilisation) neither for knowledge creation (research) nor knowledge sharing (education) (George, 2017). The research on human resource development in tourism and tourism education and 'tourism education' themed conferences across the world are area of research and discussion in recent years (Ayikoru et al. 2009 and George, 2017). Historically, tourism research has a trademark of its economic benefits and then it

shifted towards socio-cultural facets of tourism and followed by research on 'alternative form of tourism'. At present, the Indian tourism academicians are working on curriculum design, academia-industry integration and tourism faculty development through organizing different events (Jafari, 1990 and George, 2017).

1.4 Nature of Tourism Education

Tourism education is not a unified academic discipline of enquiry (Cooper and Shepherd, 1997). Jafari and Ritchie (1981), speculated tourism studies as **multi-disciplinary**. Tourism education can be more fruitful if it is 'inter-disciplinary, multi-disciplinary, trans-disciplinary or counter-disciplinary approach'. In Australia, it is practiced as 're-disciplining of tourism' or 'disciplinary colonisation'. (George, 2017). In Europe, the Erasmus Mundus European Master in Tourism Management (EMTM) is dedicated to the study of Tourism Product Development and Destination Management at The University of Girona (Spain). The Sustainable Tourism Development at University of Southern Denmark, and Tourism Policy Design, Tourism Environment Management and Economics at University of Ljubljana, Slovenia (EMTM, 2020). The curriculum of EMTM is designed to equip tourism professionals with the capability of sustainable decision making, culture diversity understanding and knowledge about future environmental issues. It can be abstracted from above discussion that specialization based tourism education help to produce tourism professionals with sustainable decision making. The Cho and Kang (2006), Tourism education is a "legitimate field of study" (p.225), growth of tourism education in South Korea fuelled by growth of tourism industry and demand for labour. The "Tourism education began as a development of technical/vocational schools in Europe. These schools emphasized the training of core competencies such as hospitality, hotel management and related business skills" (Inui et al. 2006, p.26).

A group of the researchers i.e. Leiper (1981), Jovicic (1988), Comic (1989) and Rogozinski (1985) advocates that tourism should be treated as a well-defined discipline. While Gunn, 1987; Dann et al. (1988), Jafari (1989, 1990), Morley (1990) Pearce (1993) Pearce and Butler (1993), Ritchie and Goeldner (1994) Echtner and Jamal (1997) and Tribe (1997) opposed tourism as a distinct discipline. Tribe (1997), Gunn (1987), Jafari and Ritchie (1981) argue that tourism should be treated as a field

of study. Jafari (1990), tourism studies, has developed as four platform Advocacy and Cautionary (both focus on tourism impacts), adaptability (focus on forms of development) and knowledge based (aims to study tourism holistically and in so-doing strives for the formation of a scientific body of knowledge in tourism). Evans (2001) favours the tourism studies as interdisciplinary instead of multidisciplinary approach. In addition, “Tourism is relatively a new field of study that emerged from vocational education. The nature of tourism education seems to contribute toward tourism pedagogies, driven by business and economic considerations. At the same time, this makes tourism education susceptible to social manipulation by these same forces. However, most discussions by educators and developers of tourism curricula tend to centre on a balance between a vocational and an academic focus. The discussion is often merely about efficient and effective transferability of school curricula to daily operations, overlooking the value of learning and the intangible impacts of tourism. It is clear that a focus on employability is at odds, or in conflict with, the goal of producing graduates capable of critical thinking” (Wheeler and Lankford 2006, p.33). Airey (2004), tourism education was not practiced as an identified subject of scholarship, research and teaching before 1970s. The Tourism Education Futures Initiative (TEFI) and the Building Excellence in Sustainable Tourism Education Network (BEST-EN) are working for the future of tourism education while UNWTO. TedQual (TedQual- Tourism Education Quality) is working for the quality of tourism education across the globe. Indian is still a step behind in Tourism stakeholders. Field visits, class exercises, placements and growing research activities (Airey, 2013), regarding tourism are occurring across the disciplines, which recognizes tourism education as an academia. Ayikoru (2004), “Tourism education is apparently one of the main sub sectors of the multi-sectoral tourism world and one whose manifestation could impact on the whole of tourism’s society, directly or indirectly” (p.23). Airey (2004) “Over the last forty years, education related to tourism has become established as a notable and distinct part of the repertoire of higher education” (p.9). In addition, there was not even a single knowledgeable book regarding tourism education was available till 1972. Tourism education text books were dominated by the official reports of government (Burkart and Medlik, 1974). Tribe (1999, as cited in Airey 2004) called tourism education as extra disciplinary knowledge because the source of knowledge were “industry, government, think tanks,

interest groups, research institutes and consultancies” (p.10).The UNWTO.TedQual (2013) is working on internationalisation of minds of future tourism professionals.

1.5 Education and Tourism Education

“Education develops a country’s economy and society, therefore, it is the milestone of nation’s development. Education provides knowledge and skills to the population, as well as shaping the personality of the youth of a nation” (p.443) ...thus, education is a major aspect of development of any modern society since if there is a deficit of educated people then society will stop its further progress” (Idris et.al, p. 450). Human resource is a key stone to achieve economic development of a country (Halimyar, 2018). The human resource with talent, skills and work experience from tourism industry is very essential for the success of tourism industry (Westford University, 2015). Level of education has an important role in organizing and cooperating of a community towards sharing and implementing an idea (Piekarz and Callanan, 2013). Tourism education opens the way for how a tourist destination prepares the human resources to be able to work professionally in developing the tourism sectors (Malihah and Setiyorini 2014).Tourism education plays a major role in preparing students to gain professional and practical skills required by the tourism industry. Besides former “the teaching of tourism at a higher education level has become well established in British universities” (Evans,2001, p.17). While, the BEST Education Network and the Tourism Education Futures Initiative are key players in tourism education at global platform (Moscardo, 2015a, p.1) because of their lifelong learning approach. Tourism education is very important to provide quality services and it is apparent. South Africa has implement national qualification certification for all sub sectors of tourism industry to ensure the quality services to the tourists. Tourism education has numerous roles in actual implementation of sustainable development through tourism. It can actually practice the balance among profit, people and planet. At local level, tourism education can help to stop economic leakage from host communities (by external investors) through skilling, generates local the entrepreneurs, and empowers the disadvantaged people. Tourism education helps in providing quality services and leads the visitors to satisfaction, and also inculcate respect for host culture and social practices. Through tourism education visitors’ behaviour can be changed and environment can be protected/conserved, tourism education spreads awareness about code of conduct at any destination; visitor

management (to maintain carrying capacity and damage to physical environment) and it helps in sustainable behaviour of stakeholders (UNWTO and United Nations Environment Programme-UNEP, 2005). Tourism education in India, is being practiced in universities under Vocational Studies or under armour of Faculty of Management (Dahiya, 2013). The literature shows tourism education helps in skill acquisition or to nourish the good qualities and draw out the best in every individual towards the benefits of humanity. It can be inferred that hospitality or hotel management is the component of tourism education. It mentioned, conventional tourism education have an end goal and it was employability to graduates. It is also important to make discipline research oriented to produce quality human resource. Moreover, it must be based on research and integrate curricula with and business environment, and networking among tourism industry, government.

1.6 Why Tourism Education?

Tourism education helps to improve quality of national wide tourism activities, infuse business and life skills, development towards sustainable competition, and exposure to multi culture working environment among the pursuers (Malra, 2016, slide-6). The Government, tourism business, education institute, tourism and trade associations, tourism trade media, human resource and host population are key actors of tourism (Incredible India Tourism Facilitator Certification-IITFC, 2020). Tourism education institutions work as a source of human resources for tourism businesses, because they train and develop human resource as per the tourism industry demand. Tourism education is being taught from schools to universities and full time to short term courses in the form of certificates are produced in India. As per IITFC(2020), National Council for Hotel Management and Catering Technology (NCHMCT), Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM), Indian Institute of Skiing and Mountaineering (IISM) and Indian Culinary Institute (ICI) are supported by Ministry of Tourism, Government of India. (IITFC, 2020), Tourism has potential to offer great jobs because of its growing nature and skilling can fulfil shortage of employees in tourism business. Tourism is a “people to people” industry, where performance of employees influences the experiences of the tourists. Travel and tourism industry in 2017 witnessed 41,622,500 (8%) direct jobs in India. To resolve the issue of ‘over tourism’, in urban destinations UNWTO has a strategy to ‘enhance visitors’ segmentation. Moreover, rural destinations are having

scarcity of visitors'. Sheldon et al (2011), Tourism graduates are “entering the uncertain world of the future and, in particular, the vulnerable tourism sector needs different skills, aptitudes, and knowledge to succeed” (p.3). There is need to update the curriculum and pedagogy of tourism education. As tourism world has continuum change so there is need to produce managers with quality leadership. The tourism education and tourist arrival is increasing in India because of economic reforms. There is need to train tourism graduates as per the industry and comprehensive professional literature to facilitate tourism studies. Employment is the major reason to join tourism programs (Seth, 2007) but the need for human resource development and promotion of tourism as career led to advancement of tourism education (Amoah and Baum, 1997). Indian tourism education programs are designed to attract talented students and these programs are delivered to ensure job placement for the graduates (George, 2017). There is need to revamp the essentials for success of tourism education. According to Malra (2016), Personal travel experiences, strong language and communication skills, deeper cultural and accommodation industry are the essentials for success of tourism education (slide-2). During the early years of 2000s core faculty with tourism background have started to work on key positions in tourism academia. It lead the tourism education to advancement. At present, Indian tourism curriculum is not fit for contemporary tourism industry demand. Brick and Mortar education system has transformed into hybrid one (George, 2017). In the 4th industrial revolution, there will be hybrid pedagogy i.e. global resource person will be available through teleconferencing and distance learning mode. Assessment (student) will be individualised and learning will be time bound (Inversini, 2013, slide-5).

1.7 Tourism Education in India

Tourism education in India is provided in the form of Certificate, Diploma, Advance Diploma, Bachelor Degree, Master Degree, Master of Philosophy (M Phil), Doctoral and Post-Doctoral. The awareness or knowledge creation of tourism education is taking place at Central, State, Private, Deemed Universities as well as Institutes of National Importance. The conferences, research projects and journals are among the major part of knowledge creation in the country towards tourism education. The country is witnessing the growth of tourism education as there is a paramount shift in the importance/need of tourism education. The tourism education was started from a diploma course at College of Vocational studies, Delhi University

in 1972 to Indian Institute of Management in 2020. It tried to enlist the maximum of public sector (Central/State) institutions providing tourism education in the country.

A) Tourism education at Indian Institute of Management (IIM), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) and Indian Institute of Travel and Tourism Management (IITTM)

A.1) Tourism Education in being disseminated in Indian Institute of Management (IIM)

According to IIM Sirmour (2019), the institute initiated a step to produce tourism graduates through MBA (Tourism and Hospitality). It is a two year program after 10+2+3 year degree. The objectives of the tourism program are familiarisation about ground operations, marketing and development of tourism products/services. The program has key goals to infuse business knowledge and management skills among tourism graduates. The entrepreneurship, special interest tourism, tourism planning, tourism analytics, contemporary hotel and travel management are in particular. The institute has incorporated an internship (42-48 days) provision after the completion of first year course work. There are facilities for students to have an exposure to international tourism business through International Immersion Program (IIP). The combination of lectures, flip classroom sessions, case studies, online resources, field work, project assignments, and lab sessions is the part of curriculum pedagogy. The work experience has weightage for selection in the program.

A.2) Tourism Education Knowledge creation at Indian Institute of Technology, Rurkee

According to IIT Rurkee, the Department of Management studies, is conducting research on different research problems with the dedicated faculty in the field of human resource management in tourism industry. The scholars in the department are examining the Role of Destination Personality in Predicting Tourist Behaviour (2013), Tourism (2015), and Travel Behaviour and Travel Demand Management (2018).

A.3) Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM)

IITTM is a premier institute under Ministry of Tourism, Government of India providing tourism education since 1983. The institute is devoted to higher tourism

education, quality human resource, training, research, consultation about sustainable tourism, travel and other allied sectors. There are seven institutes across the country at Gwalior, Bhubaneswar, Noida, Nellore, Goa, Shillong (camp) and Bodh Gaya (Camp) under ministry of tourism providing tourism education in different domains. The IITTM at Bhubaneswar, Gwalior, Nellore and Noida provide MBA (Tourism and Travel Management) and BBA (Tourism and Travel). The National Institute of water sports Goa has conducted 796 different training programs and trained 15860 trainees from 1990 to March 04, 2016. The Bodh Gaya Camp provides language skills in Korean, Thai, Chinese, Japanese, Burmese and Sri Lankan. The Shillong Camp to fulfil the need of tour guide in North East Region of the country. IITTM also has PhD in Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM, 2019).

B) Knowledge Creation under the sponsorship of Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR) in Tourism

The research and development projects are approved under domain, Governance, Innovation and Public Policy, Politics, Law and Economics, Growth, Macro Trade and Economic Policy, Agriculture and Rural Development and Employment Skills and Rural Transformation which also proves that tourism is a multidisciplinary in nature. Moreover, projects are sanctioned under Impactful Policy Research in Social Sciences (IMPRESS) scheme, to “identify and fund research proposals in social-sciences with maximum impact on the governance and society”. Further, tourism has marked its importance in national economy as well as into research and development. Research is being promoted in the domain of tourism because the tourism has multifaceted impact on the community development and it will lead to knowledge creation and its implementation.

Table 1.2 shows the importance of tourism is proposed with regards to ‘Rural Development’, ‘Sustainable development’ and ‘tourism destination competitiveness’ as well as empowerment and skill development among the vulnerable communities. The institutes or universities which are even not purely tourism based, but are also contributing in development of tourism education and helping the policy makers. It can be also asserted from the table that 7 projects out of 8 projects are assigned to South Indian institution. Further, South Indian States are ahead of other Indian States in context of foreign tourist arrival. It shows expenditure on research and development definitely leads to tourism growth. List of proposals approved by

Steering Committee whose Interaction / Presentation were held during April 11-May 2, 2019.

Table 1.2: Research and development under ICSSR

Sr. No.	Project Director	Project Title	Domain	Affiliation
1.	Gyanaranjan Swain	Governance and Management of Religious Tourism in India: A Comparative Study of Jagannath Temple of Odisha, Tirupati Temple of Andhra Pradesh, Sabarimala Temple of Kerala and Baishno Devi Temple of Jammu and Kashmir	Governance, Innovation and Public Policy	Ravenshaw University, Cuttak (Id: U-0361), Odisha
2.	Shanthi Marie	Sustainable Tourism – An Approach Towards Building Destination Competitiveness for Economic Development in Tamil Nadu and Kerala	Politics, Law and Economics	Government Arts College, Tiruppur (Id: C-41110), Tamil Nadu
3.	Dr. G.S Sandhya Nair	A Study on the Effect of Green Protocol Initiatives on Low Impact Tourism and Sustainable Destination Management	Governance, Innovation and Public Policy	Sree Vivekananda College, Kerala
4.	Sheena Suresh	Brand India: The Futuristic Medical Tourism hub – A “Make in India initiative”	Growth, Macro Trade and Economic Policy	National Institute of Technology, Karnataka (Id: U-0237), Karnataka
5.	Dr. Venugopalan T	Sustainable Tourism Development in India – A Case Study of Uttar Pradesh Heritage Tourism	Growth, Macro Trade and Economic Policy	University of Delhi (Id: U-0120), Delhi (NCT)
6.	Joydeep Biswas	Evaluating Tourism Destination Competitiveness (TDC)- A Case in the State of Odisha	Growth, Macro Trade and Economic Policy	KIIT, Odisha
7.	Mrutyunjay Swain	Role of Agri-Entrepreneurship and Agri-Tourism in Rural Transformation in Tribal Areas of Odisha, India: Prospects and Constraints	Agriculture and Rural Development	Khallikote University, Berhampur, Odisha
8.	Babu Rengaraj	Community Skill Enhancement Programme for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Community Members in Ecotourism Destinations in Kerala	Employment Skills and Rural Transformation	Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies, Thycad, Thiruvananthapuram (Id: C- 43655), Kerala

Source: ICSSR (2019)

C) Continuum approval of courses by UGC

Tourism education is also being imparted as vocational education. The Bachelor of Vocation (B. Voc.) course is offered and provided across the country in colleges and universities.

Table 1.3: UGC approved new colleges for B. Voc. program in tourism

S.No.	State/ colleges	Name of course
1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abhayapuri College, Assam. 	Tourism and Travel Management
2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kaliabor College, Nagaon, Assam St. Michael's College, Cherthala Mayithara, Kerala 	Tourism and Service Industry
3.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N.S. Patel Art College, Anand, Gujrat. Mount Carmel College, Autonomous, Palace Road, Bangalore, Karnataka. Madras Christian College (Autonomous) Tambaram East, Tamil Nadu Sangamner Nagarpalika Arts, D.J. Malpani Commerce and B.N. Sarada Science College, Pune Nashik Highway, Ghulewadi, Sangamner, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra 	Hospitality and Tourism
4.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> St. Xavier's College Mahapalika Mark, Mumbai-400001, Maharashtra 	Tourism
5.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jayhind College, A Road, Church Gate, Bomaby, Maharashtra 	Travel and Tourism Management
6.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thoubal College, Manipur Little Flower College, Madurai, Tamilnadu Waghire College, A/P: Saswad, Tahsil-Purandar, Maharashtra North Gauhati College, College Nagar, Guwahati, Assam. H.R. College of Commerce and Economics, Churchgate, Mumbai, Maharashtra 	Tourism and Hospitality Management
7.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hindi Mahavidyalaya, O.U road, Hyderabad, Telangana 	Hospitality and Tourism Administration
8.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ramnagar College, Purba Medinipur West Bengal. 	Hospitality and Tourism Management

Source: UGC (2015).

The approved list of courses in different colleges/universities during 2015 is mentioned in table 1.3

It can be understood from the table that tourism education is provided across the country. The curriculum of the program is similar but different in nomenclature. The UGC has approved tourism education programs in colleges just with an alphabetic rearrangements or elimination.

The University Grant Commission (UGC) is the authority to grant approval for courses. During the recent few years UGC has approved the Advance Diploma/Diploma programs in tourism at some new institutions/colleges. According to the UGC (2015) the following colleges across the country are approved to provide tourism education through Advance Diploma or Diploma courses.

Table 1.4: UGC approved community colleges for tourism education

S.No.	College(s)	Course approved
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • St. Aloysius College, Manglore, Karnataka. • City College, Raja Rammohan Sarai, Kolkata. • Maynaguri College, Jaipauri. 	Diploma in Travel and Tourism
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marain College, Kerala 	Diploma in Tourism and Hospitality
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N.S. Patel Arts College, Gujrat 	Advance Diploma in Hospitality and Tourism
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharadchandra Arts and Commerce College, Nagpur • Bhartiya Jain Sanghatana's Arts, Science and Commerce College, Pune. 	Diploma in Hospitality and Tourism
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jawaharlal Nehru College, Arunachal Pradesh • B.H. College, Assam 	Diploma in tourism
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mugberia Gangadhar Mahavidyalaya, Medinipur West Bengal 	Diploma in Tourism and Hotel Management
7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government (Autonomous) College, Bhawanipatna, Orisa 	Diploma in Tourism and Hospital Management
8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • St. Joseph College, Jakhama, Nagaland 	Diploma in Tourism and Service Industry
9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dimapur Govt. College, Nagaland. • D.D. (Autonomous) College, Orisa. • Fakir Mohan (Autonomous) College, Orisa. • Maharaja Purna Chandra College; Orisa 	Diploma in Tourism and Hospitality Management
10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ahmednagar College, Maharashtra provided 	Diploma in Travel and Tourism Management

Source: UGC, 2015.

D) State Universities and Tourism Education Programs

The application of tourism in different disciplines is beautifully applied by majority of State Universities. The Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS) affiliated to University of Kerala has most diversified tourism education programs.

Table 1.5: Tourism Education in State Universities

Sr.No.	University	Courses offered
1.	Acharya Nagarjuna University, Andhra Pradesh	M.T.T.M (2005-06), M Phil and Ph.D.(2013-14)
2.	Adikavi Nannaya University, Andhra Pradesh	MBA (Tourism and Hospitality Management)
3.	Annamalai University, Tamil Nadu	Distance learning Programs are M.Sc. Tourism, M.B.A. Hotel Management and Tourism, B.Sc Hotel Management and Tourism and B.B.A Hospitality and Tourism Management.
4.	Assam Women's University	Master of Tourism and Travel Management MTTM
5.	Awadhesh Pratap Singh University, Rewa, Madhya Pradesh	MBA(Tourism Administration), MPhil (Tourism Administration) under Departments of Ancient Indian History
6.	Baba Gulam Singh Badshah University, Jammu and Kashmir	Diploma in Travel and Tourism Management, B. Voc. Tourism and Travel Management, MBA (Hospitality and Tourism), M. Phil. Ph. D.
7.	Bardhwan University, West Bengal	Master of Business Administration (Tourism), Ph.D. in Tourism Management
8.	Barkatula University, Madhya Pradesh	MPIHTTMS-BBA (Tourism), PGD in Tourism and Hotel Management
9.	Bengaluru University, Karnataka	Master of Tourism And Travel Management, PG Diploma in Tourism and Museology, PhD (Faculty of History)
10.	Bharathidasan University, Tamil Nadu	B.A. Tourism And Travel Management
11.	Bhartiyar University, Tamil Nadu	M.B.A. Tourism and Hotel Management, B.A. Tourism and Travel Management, As applied subject under M.A. History.
12.	Bundelkhand University, Utter Pradesh	BBA (Tourism), MBA (Tourism)
13.	Calicut University, Kerala	B.A Travel And Tourism Management, MTTM
14.	CUSAT Kochi, Kerala	MBA (Travel and Tourism)
15.	Devi Ahilya University, Madhya Pradesh	Integrated MBA (Tourism), Two Years- MBA (Tourism)
16.	Dibrugarh University, Assam	PGDTM, Masters in Travel and Tourism Management MTTM, PhD
17.	Dr Bhimrao Ambedker University, Utter Pradesh	BA(Vocational)- Travel and Tourism Management, MBA(TTM), PGDHTM,
18.	Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Open	P.G. Diploma in Culture and Heritage Tourism

	University, Telangana	
19.	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Maharashtra	Master of Tourism Administration
20.	Dravidian University, Andhra Pradesh.	MA (Tourism Management) under History, P.G. Diploma in Tourism, Archaeology and Culture Department.
21.	Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University	B. Voc. Tourism and Hospitality Management
22.	Himachal Pradesh Technical University.	MBA in Tourism and Hospitality
23.	Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla.	Master in Tourism (MTTM), Five Year (Bachelor + Master) Integrated Course in Tourism Management (FYICTTM), PhD in Tourism
24.	Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University Hyderabad	MBA in Tourism and Hospitality Management. BBA in Tourism and Hospitality Management (4 years) (offered by National Institute of Tourism and Hospitality Management). Master of Tourism Management by affiliated colleges.
25.	Jiwaji University, Madhya Pradesh	PhD, MBA(TA), BTA
26.	Kakatiya University, Telangana	MTM (1999-2000), PhD (Tourism Management)
27.	Kannur University, Kerala	BA Travel and Tourism Management, BTM, BBA-TTM, MTTM,
28.	Karnatak University, Dharwad, Karnataka	Integrated MTA (Faculty of Management), MTTM run by Karnatak Arts College Dharwad.
29.	Kashmir University, Jammu and Kashmir	Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism Management (distance), MTTM, M.Phil/PhD/3Year Integrated PhD (Tourism Management)
30.	Kavempu University, Karnataka	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBA (Tourism and Travel Management) with Travel Agency and Tour Operation Management. • MBA (Tourism and Travel Management) with Tourism and Hospitality Management • PhD
31.	Khallikote University, Odisha	MBA in Travel and Tourism Management
32.	Kumaon University	MBA (Tourism), PhD (Tourism)
33.	Kurukshetra University, Haryana	MTTM, PhD (Tourism Management)
34.	Lucknow University	BBA (Tourism), Master of Tourism and Travel Management
35.	Madurai Kamraj University, Tamil Nadu	BSc-Tourism and Hospitality Management, MBA(Tourism and Hotel Management), MSc-Tourism and Hotel Management, PG Diploma in Tourism Management, MA(Tourism Management), M Phil(Tourism and Hotel Management), PhD(Tourism Management)
36.	Maharashi Dayanand Saraswati University, Ajmer	B.Voc. Tourism and Travel Management
37.	Maharishi Dayanand University, Haryana	MTTM, BTM, PhD, M Phil

38.	Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD-under management faculty, Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM) with specialization in Aviation Management, Tour Operations and Health Tourism • B.A Tourism and Travel Management- St. Thomas College. • B.Com. (Tourism)-SH college, St. Xavier's College for Women. • B.Com. (Travel and Tourism)-Bishop Abraham Memorial College. • B.Com. Model II (Voc. Travel and Tourism)-Guru Narayana College of Arts and Science. • B.Com. Model II (Voc. Travel and Tourism)-18 colleges. • B.Com. Model III (Travel and Tourism) - Bharata Matha College. • B.Voc. Tourism and Hospitality- Sree Sankara College. • M.Sc. Hotel Management and Tourism- Mount Royal College
39.	Mangalore University, Karnataka	MBA (Tourism and Travel Management)
40.	Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tamil Nadu	Master of Tourism Management, B.A Tourism and Hospitality Management, Advance Diploma in Tourism and Travel Management.
41.	Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University of Technology, WB	BBA Tourism and Travel Management, Master of Tourism and Travel Management,
42.	Mysore University	BBA (Tourism and Travel Management), MA-Ancient History and Archaeology (from Heritage Tourism and Travel Management), PGD in Heritage Tourism and Travel Management, PGD in Museology, Tourism and Heritage (DoS in Ancient History and Archaeology), PGD in Tourism Management, PhD (Tourism-at Appa Research Centre, Gulbarga)
43.	Nagpur University	Post-Graduate Diploma in Travel and Tourism (it was started in 1985 under Department of Ancient Indian History, culture and Archaeology) M. A. Master in Travel and Tourism
44.	Nalanda Open University, Bihar.	BA Honours (Tourism)
45.	Panjab University, Chandigarh.	Bachelor of Tourism and Travel Management (BTTM), Masters in Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM).
46.	Periyar University, Tamilnadu	BSc in Aviation and Tourism, BSc Hotel Management and Tourism, MBA (Hotel and Tourism Management), Diploma in Tourism Management (Periyar Institute of Distance Education, Periyar University)
47.	Potti Sreeramulu Telugu University, Andhra Pradesh	PG Diploma in Travel and Tourism under department of culture and tourism, MA Tourism Management (Distance)
48.	Ravenshaw University, Odisha	MBA (Hospitality and Tourism)
49.	Tamil Nadu Open	B.A. Tourism and Travel Studies, Certificate in Wildlife

	University	Tourism Guide (10 th pass), M.A. Tourism and Travel Studies. Tourism as a subject under MA-History, B.A History and Heritage Management and BSc Geography.
50.	University of Jammu, Jammu and Kashmir	MBA (Hospitality and Tourism Management), PhD (Hospitality and Tourism Management)
51.	University of Kerala	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B. Voc. Tourism and Hospitality Management-2015 • Under graduate-Commerce and Tourism and Travel Management-2014 • MBA (Tourism), PhD under Management Department. • Mar Ivanios College, Thiruvananthapuram –MTM • Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS)-MBA (Travel and Tourism), Post Graduate Diploma in Public Relations in Tourism-PGDPRT, BBA (TM), Diploma in Logistics Management, Diploma in Airport Operations, Speciality Certificate Programme in Flora and Fauna Focussed Trekking (15 days).
52.	University of Ladakh	Masters in Tourism and Travel Management
53.	University of Madras	Diploma in Travel and Tourism Management. Tourism is studied as at least one subject under M.A. Ancient History And Archaeology, M.A. Historical Studies, M. Phil. Ancient History And Archaeology, M.A. Sociology, M.A. French and M.A. Tamil Studies
54.	Utkal University, Odisha	MBA in Rural Management (Rural Tourism Management), MA History and MPhil (Application of History in Tourism).Master in Tourism and Heritage Management (MTHM-2007).
55.	Utkal University of Culture, Odisha	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bachelor in Tourism and Travel Management (BTTM) • Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM)
56.	Uttarakhand Open University	Diploma in Tourism Studies, BTTM, MTTM, PhD (Tourism Management)
57.	Vikrama Simhapuri University, Andhra Pradesh	Master of Tourism Management
58.	YCMO University, Maharashtra	B.B.A. (Aviation, Hospitality and Travel and Tourism Management), Diploma in Aviation, Hospitality and Travel and Tourism Management
59.	Yogi Vemana University, Andhra Pradesh	M.A. (History and Archaeology)- Tourism and Museology, Principles Of Tourism And Travel Management

Source: UGC, Individual University Website.

Besides, the above-mentioned State Universities, the following colleges are also producing tourism graduates through different courses in the country. The Pragjyotish College and Jagiroad College are affiliated to Gauhati University and run Master in Tourism Management (MTM) program while Jawaharlal Nehru Rajkeeya Mahavidyalaya (JNRM), Port Blair have BBA in Tourism and Travel Management. The other colleges are Kumari Mayawati Government Girls Post Graduate College, Utter Pradesh (B. Voc. HTM); Sri Guru Teg Bahadur Khalsa College, Sri Anandpur Sahib, Punjab and Government Degree College Sopore, Jammu and Kashmir; are contributing in tourism education. The government colleges of different States have

tourism education and affiliated to respective State universities e.g. Sikkim, Haryana, Uttrakhand, and Himachal Pradesh

E) Central Universities and Tourism Education Programs

As the tourism industry is growing, at the same time, there is an intense competition amongst international and domestic destinations. Quality of services is one of the reasons to magnetise the destination to attract the tourist and it is furnished through educational and professional exposure. Table 1.6 shows, there are 28 central universities providing tourism education. 15 Central Universities have introduced PhD programs in tourism. The college of vocational studies started Diploma programme in 1972 and followed by HNGBU. The HNGBU started tourism education with Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism and Pilgrimage Studies in 1976 (When it was state university). The Universities like, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) have more than 20,000 students enrolled in both tourism and hospitality programmes. The department of tourism at Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI) University has most diversified tourism education programs. The Pondicherry University can be considered as most innovative in the context of student exchange programme.

Table 1.6: Tourism Education in Central Universities

S.No.	Central University	Courses offered/affiliated
1.	Aligarh Muslim University	Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM)
2.	Assam University	Master of Business Administration in Hospitality and Tourism (MBA-HT) PhD (Hospitality and Tourism Management)
3.	Banaras Hindu University, Utter Pradesh	B Voc. (Hospitality and Tourism Management), Master of Tourism and Travel Management(MTTM), M. Voc. (Hospitality and Tourism Management), Post Graduate Diploma in Travel and Tourism Management, Diploma in Tourism Management (Part Time-2-years), PhD (Tourism Management).
4.	Bangaluru Central University	B.Com. (Tourism), M.Com. (Master of Tourism And Travel Management)
5.	Central University of Karnataka	MBA Tourism and Travel Management
6.	Central University of Kerala	MBA Tourism and Hospitality Management
7.	Central University of Andhra Pradesh	B. A. (Vocational studies) - Tourism and Travel Management.
8.	Central University of Haryana	MTTM (Master of Travel and Tourism Management), PhD
9.	Central University of Himachal Pradesh	PhD MBA(Tourism and Travel)
10.	Central University of Jammu	Integrated MPhil-PhD, (Tourism and Travel Management), MBA (Travel and Tourism Management), B. Voc. (Tourism Management)

11.	Central University of Kashmir	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Master of Travel and Tourism Management (MTTM), Integrated M Phil/PhD. • B. Voc. (Tourism and Hospitality Management).
12.	Central University of Mizoram	MBA (Tourism Marketing, Special Interest Tourism, Tourism Management)- started in 2019-20.
13.	Central University of Tamil Nadu	MBA- Tourism and Hospitality Management
14.	Central University Tripura	Master of Tourism Administration (MTA). MA/MSc Geography and Disaster Management (Geography of Tourism) under Department of Geography and Disaster Management
15.	Delhi University	Department of Adult Continuing Education and Extension Faculty of Social Sciences and Center for Professional and Technical Training run Certificate Course in Travel and Tourism. The College of Vocational Studies started diploma in tourism in 1972- At present it provides BA (Vocational Studies)-Tourism Management. There are courses like PGD in tourism management, Certificate Course in tourism and Certificate Course in Travel and Tourism.
16.	Hemwati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Utrkhand	Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism and Pilgrimage Studies (PGDTPS-1976), Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism and Elementary Hoteliering (PGDTH), MBA (TOURISM), PhD (Tourism)
17.	Indira Gandhi National Open University, Delhi	Diploma in Tourism Studies (DTS), Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM), B.A. (Vocational Studies) Tourism Management (BAVTM), Certificate in Tourism Studies (CTS), PhD (Tourism and Hospitality)
18.	Indira Gandhi National Tribal University, Madhya Pradesh	MBA (Tourism), PhD (Tourism)
19.	Jamia Millia Islamia, Delhi	M.Phil/Ph.D.(Tourism and Hospitality), Master(Tourism and Travel Management) (MTTM), MBA (Tourism and Travel), Bachelor of Tourism and Travel Management (BTTM), Diploma in Tourism and Travel Management, Certificate in (Medical and Wellness Tourism, Tour Management, Tour Guiding and Leadership, Ticketing and Airfare Construction)
20.	Manipur University	Master in Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM), B. Voc. (Tourism and Hospitality Management)
21.	North Eastern Hill University, Meghalaya	Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM). PhD (Tourism and Hotel Management).
22.	Pondicherry University	M.B.A (Tourism) Ph.D. (Tourism Studies)
23.	Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh	Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism Management (PGDTM)
24.	Sikkim University	MTTM (Masters of Tourism and Travel Management), M. Phil Tourism, Ph. D Tourism, MPhil (Geography of Tourism) under Department of Geography.
25.	Tezpur University, Assam	P.G. Diploma in Tourism Management (PGDTM), Master of Tourism and Travel Management (MTTM), PhD (M.T.M. / M.T.A./M.T.T.M)
26.	University of Allahabad	PGD Tourism Administration Under Department of Geography
27.	University of Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh	PhD (Tourism and Hospitality Management) Under School of Management.

28.	Vishvabharti University, West Bengal	Diploma in Rural Tourism under Department of Lifelong Learning and Extension (Rural Extension Centre)
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Source: UGC, Individual University Websites

*the list was limited public universities (Central/State) and to those courses having at least ‘Tourism’ is as a key word in course title.

**information about the tourism programs in concerned institute are limited to the university website information.

There is confusion with in organisations for the accreditation of tourism program like MA tourism, MTA, MTTM, MBA (Travel and Tourism). It is creating hurdle in the standardisation of tourism education program. More over the content of the programme overlaps at bachelor and master programs in the country. For the standardisation of the program different stakeholders must be included for curriculum development in the country and regularisation of tourism education under single body with regionals branches.

1.8 Indian Competitiveness at Global Platform.

Travel and tourism accounts for 5% (2017) of India’s employment. The overall travel and tourism competitive index of India is improving. The ranking for ‘Cultural Resources and Business Travel’ at 8th rank (2019) globally. As per the report it implies that there is ‘digital demand’ for cultural and entertainment events and this demand can be converted into ‘tourism products’. In addition number of world heritage cultural sites, oral and intangible cultures sites and stadium are taken into account. It can be analysed from the table 1.7that India really needs to work on environment sustainability, development of services i.e. quality services to the tourism stakeholders; health and hygiene; safety and security and use of information and communication technology in tourism industry as well as in nation. The poor service infrastructure availability for the tourists shows the big lacuna in tourism planning towards destination development and catering the needs of tourists in sustainable way. Hence, there is need to develop visionary destination planners, and the need can be fulfilled through a lifelong tourism education.

With regards to prioritisation of travel and tourism industry in 2017, among 136 countries Indian Government prioritization of travel and tourism industry ranked 102,government expenditure for travel and tourism (% government budget) ranked125,effectiveness of marketing and branding to attract tourists (94)and there is

need to improve country brand strategy (81). It demands for human resources with real time actionable expertise. With regards to human resources and labour market (76th rank among 104 countries); India stands out of the top ten Asia Pacific countries (2019). It implies that ease of finding skilled employees, extent of staff training and female participation need to be improved.

Table 1.7: Brief of travel and tourism competitive index toward India

Parameter	2013 (140)	2015 (141)	2017 (136)	2019 (140)
TTCI ranking	65	52	40	34
Business environment	125	107	89	39
Safety and security	74	129	114	122
Health and Hygiene	109	106	104	106
Human resource and Labour market	96	111	87	76
ICT readiness	111	114	112	105
Prioritisation of travel and tourism	98	96	104	94
International Openness	--	69	55	51
Price competitiveness	20	8	10	13
Environmental sustainability	107	139	134	128
Air transport Infrastructure	39	35	32	33
Ground and port infrastructure	42	50	110	28
Tourist Service Infrastructure	109	109	110	109
Natural Resources	9	17	24	14
Cultural resources and business travel	24	10	9	8

Source: World Economic Forums' Travel and Tourism Competitiveness reports (2013, 2015, 2017 and 2019)

*TTCI-Travel and Tourism Competitive Index, ICT- Information and Communication Technology

According to Televisory (2020), the 4th industrial revolution has led to the coexistence of clients and travel brands. The website will be the heart of any organization in future. The Social media campaign and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are changing the skill set i.e. cultural and digital skills. The major online travel platforms are actively using AI to forecast the best routes and buy the cheapest tickets. The catering of unique experiences for to the clients are in demand. It has fuelled the demand to learn the skill of today and tomorrow. Because the students of today are tomorrow's professionals. Indian ICT readiness is ranked at 105 out of 140 countries (WTTC, 2019). While the globe is heading towards 'digital strategy' (WTTC, 2017).

In terms of direct and total GDP, Indian tourism industry is predicted as 3rd largest travel and tour economy globally till 2028 (WTTC, 2018). It will bring more

traffic and consequently more business and more jobs as well, because tourists will demand for sightseeing, accommodation, food and places to explore and etc. It will raise challenges to market with challenges of fleets, ATM, Airports and human resource. The ranking of India with regards to Human Resource and labour market is 76th position among 140 economies (WTTC, 2019).

Tourism world is dynamic and issues like war in Syria, Arizona fire, supersonic spacecraft, and coronavirus all are impacting tourism and can lead to tourism recession as well as innovation in future travelling. While Prioritisation of Travel and Tourism is placed at 94th among 140 nations.

With regards to Safety and Security pillar, India is placed at 122 rank, which is really a point of concern. Tourists will come to India if they are welcomed and to develop that culture there is need to promote tourism education for all the stakeholders of tourism industry.

E.g. Tourism education → Taxi driver → Bilingual → good tourism.

E.g. Tourist → Welcoming → culture → Sustainable income.

To develop the culture of welcoming warmly to tourists there is need to focus on specialized tourism education, establishment of tourism institutes which can cater the growing demand of tourism industry. Skilling India for tourism is new game with new rules

1.9 Academia-Industry Networking in Promoting Tourism Education, Knowledge Creation-Sharing

The United States had aggressively been promoting Academia-Industry networking since 1970s for social, academia and industry benefits (Jones, 2020). In India, different education institutes are leveraging tourism education through industry institute synergy and upskilling of faculty. It is found that IITTM and Institute of Hotel Management (IHM) are the key players in promotion of tourism education across India through different programs sponsored by Ministry of Tourism, Government of India. Although the contribution of different Indian Universities into tourism knowledge creation and sharing is also a considerable step. It is also debatable that private players and Universities' cooperation towards research and

sensitisation programs is far behind than government players. The majority of travel trade organizations are in the private sector and have made a big profit share (Balal and Petrescu, 2011).

- a) **Bournemouth University - UNWTO:** Working on tourism program 'Ethics in tourism' and guidance to 'World Heritage site' Destination development Professionals.
- b) **Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna University-Namami Gange:** The University is working with State Government of Uttarakhand under 'Namami Gange' Project. It involves sensitisation of people to keep the river clean and cleaning the Ganga river (Hindustan Times, 2017).
- c) **Indian Institute of Travel and Tourism Management(s)-Ministry of Tourism:** IITTM is conducting pan India sensitisation program under Ministry of Tourism and in cooperation with different States governments about 'adopt a heritage', 'Guided Heritage walk', 'Workshop on Travel Writing and Photography', 'Nukkad-Natak', 'Quiz, Essay, Debate and Painting Competitions for School Students', 'Awareness Talk and sensitisation of with Auto Rickshaw/taxi Drivers', 'Swach Paryatan', 'Excursion tour for students', 'workshop on cleanliness at tourism destination', and 'indigenous product promotion.'
- d) **Institute of Hotel Management(s)-Ministry of Tourism:** Destination specific Run for incredible India programs for students and stakeholders,, Tourism Rally, Atithi devo Bhava Sensitization Programme for street vendors, rickshaw and auto rickshaw drivers, distribution of trash bags, Nukkad-Natak, Illumination around Site, Quiz / Essay / Painting Competitions for students Sensitisation Programmes for Stakeholders, Hygiene Awareness among tourists, street food vendors, other unorganised sector stakeholders, guided heritage tours, Excursion tour for students.
- e) **Central University of Kashmir, Jammu and Kashmir:** Ministry of Tourism- Seminar on -Sustainable Tourism - A Tool for Development.
- f) **Pondicherry University:** Workshop on-Sustainable Tourism for Inclusive Growth of Rural Areas.

- g) **University of Hyderabad:** Workshop on “Changing Paradigms in Tourism Management - Prospects and Challenges.
- h) **HNGBU:** Seminar on-Sustainable Entrepreneurship Development in Tourism and Hospitality Sector in Uttarakhand.
- i) **University of Allahabad:** Seminar on- Changing Paradigms in Indian Tourism Challenges for Growth and Sustainability.
- j) **Aligarh Muslim University:** Workshops on: Legal and regulatory aspect of tourism (West Asia and Tourism) (Source: Ministry of tourism).

There is need to identify the common interest of academia and industry. Linkage of Tourism education development with National plan through massive plans, directions, goals, guidelines for region wise development with more technical facets of tourism towards local development through implementing actions. For example the university can adopt a village/destination. The university will provide technical support to the destination/village development, which is a step towards National development. George (2017), has revealed that refresher courses are attended and conducted in India but more career promotion centric than knowledge creation. Hence, workshops, seminars and conferences are also conducted towards career promotion rewards than actual aim towards education advancement.

1.10 Different Agencies Revamping Skills in Indian Tourism Industry

a) Tourism and Hospitality Skill Council (THSC)

According to THSC, the council is skilling India to bridge the supply demand gap in tourism industry through flag ship schemes i.e. Skill India Program. The Ministry of Skill Development and Employment is sponsoring THSC through National Skill Development Corporation. THSC is enroute to achieve its mission through establishing Center of Excellence (COE), Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra (PMKVY), Pradhan Mantri Mahila Kaushal Kendra (PMMKK) and India Internal Skill Center (IISC). During 2018-2019, 1245 Training Centers, 269-PMKVY, 1-COE and 12 self-funded institutes to meet the goal of THSC are enlisted. THSC caters to all the sub sectors of the tourism industry i.e. Hotels, Tour Operators, Food Service Restaurants, Facilities Management and Cruise Liners. It is creating an eco-system of

skill development as per the demand of tourism industry. It has a mission to produce a big workforce of more than 3.3 million by 2022 through establishment of National Occupational Standards, Labour Market Information System, Accreditation of training partners / vocational institutions, Certification of Trainers and facilitation of learner assessments and certifications. It also has a ‘skill grid’ and can be used by tourism industry to hire skilled human resource as per the need of employers. There are 18658 THSC certified candidates available to be hired by tourism industry.

THSC has collaboration with 40 different college and 400 industry partners across India and provides curriculum. THSC provides the program structure and curriculum which is combination of general component and skill development component. The Bachelor of Vocation (B.Voc.) is one of the flagship program for skills development recognised by The University Grants Commission (UGC) and 10+2 schooling is entry eligibility. It is launched to skills development based higher education, leading to Bachelor of Vocation (B.Voc.) degree with multiple exits such as Diploma (6-month-level-4), Certificate (1 year-level 5), Advance Diploma (2 years-level-6) and Degree (3 years- level-7) and lead to Master of Vocation (M. Voc.) (THSC, 2020).

Table 1.8: Various Skill India Programs (tourism).

S.No.	Name of the QP	NSQF Level	Notional Hours
1.	Assistant Catering Manager	6	475
2.	Assistant Facility Manager	7	435
3.	Bartender	5	320
4.	Base Camp Manager	6	480
5.	Bell Captain	5	300
6.	Billing Executive	4	290
7.	Bungee Jump Guide	5	390
8.	Captain	6	500
9.	Chef-de-partie	6	285
10.	Cleaner – Carpet and Chair	4	180
11.	Cleaner-Roadside Eatery	1	250
12.	Commi 1	5	500
13.	Commis Chef	4	500
14.	Counter Sale Executive	4	240
15.	Cruise-Boat Jetty In-charge	5	300
16.	Duty Manager	7	440
17.	Facility Management Executive	6	430
18.	Facility Supervisor	5	365

19.	Facility Store Keeper	4	220
20.	Food & Beverage Service- Steward	4	300
21.	F&B Service Trainee	3	435
22.	Front Office Associate	4	340
23.	Front Office Executive	5	495
24.	Guest House Caretaker	5	370
25.	Guest Relations Manager	6	440
26.	Heritage Tour Guide	4	330
27.	Bell Boy	4	340
28.	Housekeeping Attendant (Manual Cleaning)	3	250
29.	Housekeeping Executive	5	350
30.	Housekeeping Manager	7	400
31.	Housekeeping Supervisor	6	220
32.	Kitchen Helper	2	300
33.	Kitchen Steward	3	200
34.	Laundry Machine Operator	4	240
35.	Laundry Valet	3	300
36.	Meet & Greet officer	4	260
37.	Meeting, Conference and Event Planner	5	205
38.	Mountaineering Camp Cook/ Camp Cook	4	240
39.	Multi-cuisine Cook	4	580
40.	Outlet Manager	7	500
41.	Paragliding Coach	6	450
42.	Pest Controller	4	200
43.	Procurement Executive (FM)	5	200
44.	Dishwasher	1	180
45.	Home Delivery Boy	3	200
46.	Order Taker-Home Delivery	4	340
47.	Tandoor Cook	3	350
48.	Room Attendant	4	300
49.	Sous Chef	7	520
50.	Street Food Vendor	4	290
51.	Surface Polisher	4	240
52.	Team Leader	6	400
53.	Ticketing Consultant	5	240
54.	Tour Escort	4	330
55.	Tour Guide	4	420
56.	Tour Manager	6	390
57.	Tour Vehicle Driver	4	300
58.	Trainee Chef	3	400
59.	Transport Coordinator	5	300
60.	Travel Consultant	4	220
61.	Travel Insurance Executive	3	230
62.	Visa Assistance Consultant	4	210
63.	Water Tank Cleaner	4	270

Source: The Tourism and Hospitality Skill Council

*National Skill Qualification Framework (NSQF)

b) Indian Institute of Heritage and Conservation under Ministry of Culture

According to The Economic Times (2020), Budget 2020-2021, proposed the setting up of an Indian Institute of Heritage and Conservation with the status of a deemed university under the Ministry of Culture. It is a process for synergy of tourism education and culture to make India world leading destination. The University will provide training and educational programs in tourism, promote research and created repository of literature in tourism studies.

c) National Tourism University under Ministry of Tourism

The ministry of tourism forecasted to establish a National tourism university by June 2015. It will promote research, create repository of literature in tourism studies and will award degree to IITTM Indian Culinary Institute and National Museum Institutes (The Times of India, 2015). The plan is still awaited to be executed. It shows the negligence of policy makers and negligence towards the importance of tourism education and research.

d) Ministry of Tourism Sponsored Tourism Education Programs

The State tourism departments and the Ministry of Tourism, Government of India have also been playing an important role to produce a human resource to meet the needs of the tourism industry in the country. The Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, sponsors tourism education programs and tourism professionals' up-skilling in India, in collaboration with Hotel Management and Catering Technology and Applied Nutrition (IHMs-46; 21 Central, 25 State), Food Craft Institutes (FCIs-14), Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM) and National Council of Hotel Management and Catering Technology (NCHMCT). NCHMCT regulates Government IHMs and FCIs along with 24 private IHMs. 3-year B.Sc. programme in Hospitality and Hotel Administration, 2-years-M.Sc. in Hospitality Administration course, i.e. P.G. Diploma in Accommodation Operation, P.G. Diploma in Dietetics and Hospital Food Service, Diploma in Food Production; Diploma in Food and Beverage Service; Diploma in House Keeping

Operation, Diploma in Bakery and Confectionery, Craftsmanship Course in Food and Beverage Service and Certificate Course in Hotel and Catering Management are regulated by the council. During the year 2019-2020, total 12,556 students enrolled themselves under various regular academic programs offered by NCHMCT. An overview of the nature of tourism programs being provided by Ministry of Tourism, Government India in various institutes is provided in table no. 1.9.

Table 1.9: Tourism Education Programs of Ministry of Tourism.

Sr. No.	Institutes for Human Resource Development Program	Name of the programs	Purpose of Human Resource Development Program
1.	Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM)	MBA (TTM), BBA (TT), PhD	Specialized training and education. Skill development
2.	IITTM Camp Bodh Gaya and Shillong	Language and Guiding courses	Skill development
3.	Indian Culinary Institute (ICI)	BBA Culinary Art	To promote culinary research, specialized training and preservation of culinary Art
4.	Institute of Hotel Management (IHM)	BSc HHA, MSc HA	Human resource
5.	Food Craft Institute (FCI)	Food craft courses	Skill level education in Hospitality Industry
6.	Capacity Building for Service Providers (CBSP)	Hunar se Rozgar Tak, Skill Testing and Certification, Entrepreneurship Program,	Train and upgrade manpower at every level i.e. to direct service providers or to teachers, administrators and trainers and other service providers, employable skills among youth
7.	Schools/ ITI/colleges/Universities/PSUs	Vocational Courses	To take tourism and hospitality education into mainstream. Central assistance is there w.r.t fulfilment of guidelines
8.	Other Programs are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourism Awareness programs • Sanitation Programs,, • language programs for tour and tourist facilitators, • Tourism Adventure and Travel Adventure Escort programs, Regional Guides 		Around 17 iconic places for Dhabawalas, Taxi/ Rickshaw Drivers, Police Staff, Hotel Staff and shop keepers etc.

Source: Ministry of Tourism, Government of India.

* BSc HHA- Bachelor of Science Hospitality and Hotel Administration, MSc HA-Master of Science Hospitality Administration. ITI-industrial Training institutes, PSUs- Public sector Units, MBA (TTM)-Master of Business Administration (Tourism and Travel Management), BBA (TT), Bachelor of Business Administration (Tourism Travel), PhD-Doctor of Philosophy, ITI-Industrial Training Institute, PSUs-Public Sector Units.

BSc HHA, BBA Culinary Art and BBA (TT) is offered after 10+2 of schooling and these are three years programs. The selection process in BSc HHA is through National Council for Hotel Management Joint Entrance Examination (NCHM-JEE) regularized by National Council for Hotel Management and Catering Technology (NCHMCT), Noida, India and conducted by National Testing Agency (NTA). Besides this NCTHM, private, deemed, State and Central universities also offer bachelor programs in hotel management along with affiliated to colleges and institutes under University Grant Commission (UGC). The MBA (TTM) is a two years program and offered after 10+2+3 of education. Table 1.9 shows that the specialization of tourism programs at IITTM is restricted to tourism and travel alone and there is need to diversify the area of specialisations in tourism programs. During the year 2019-2020, total 628 students enrolled themselves under various regular academic programs offered by IITTM (Ministry of Tourism, 2020). It is found that Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, is producing and training a wide range of manpower from ground handlers to policymakers. The programs vary from short term courses to regular degrees. Yet, there is a gap in produced human resource and the skilled resource required by the industry. It is also found that multiple agencies are deciding the program structure and curriculum; and multiple exists for same degree promote vocationalisation of tourism education and degrade the rapport of programs. Airey (2004) has mentioned that “Tourism education is not simply about vocationalism” (p.11). Hence, there is need to establish a National Tourism University (NTU) with regional and overseas branches.

1.11 Lacuna in Indian Tourism Education

Aspects which are pulling down the advancement of tourism education in India are lack of valid and peer reviewed empirical research, course curriculum designing by Universities for affiliated colleges, most of the master students have no industry experience (less networking with professionals from industry), Indian tourism industry failed to pay alluring perks to the tourism graduates, academicians are failed to sensitise the students towards opportunities and challenge in tourism industry, students are not encouraged for part time jobs during the study

(income/exposure to work life), general tourism programs with different nomenclature, lack of quality assessment unlike West (where dedicated tourism universities are available), lack of intrinsic motivation among professors towards knowledge creation, lack of Inter institution partnership for knowledge sharing and refreshers courses for academicians are available but attended by academicians because of its requirement for promotion (George, 2007). There are no all India tourism services for tourism graduates (Sofique, 2013). There is a recommendation that there is a need to improve tourism education for sustainability (Moscardo, 2015b). Chen (2014), academic study of tourism education is mature but there is a “big gap in market demand” (p.40). These gaps prevail in India because of poor curriculum design, lack of practical and outdated teaching style are major problems in Indian universities providing tourism education. It lags behind the tourism development needs. The expansion of enrolment does not meet the industry demands. To meet industry needs, there is a need to reform teaching, curriculum, pedagogy and to inculcate scientific temperament in students. To bridge the gap between industry and academia, case study based on education, modern infrastructure, research wing to understand the industry scenario, various student evaluation modes (other than paper system) and teachers with industry experience are needed. Masters in a foreign language can be an edge. As sustainable tourism development practices help policy makers to provide long-lasting benefits to the society; sustainable tourism operations can result into growth of income and as it stimulates healthy competition in concerned industry. (UNWTO, 2018). The most of the Indian academicians as well as institutes don't want to wind against the current. There is a need to re-examine the academicians (George, 2017). Higher tourism education is growing in country, professional and vocational institutes are producing human resource to a great extent but policy planners are ill defined over the nature of tourism education (Dahiya, 2013).

1.12 Tourism Education- For whom?

There is more need to spread awareness among companies, destinations, and travellers for their impact on host communities and environment (Mullis, 2017). It was argued that “All stakeholders within tourism should be educated about the need

to develop more sustainable form of tourism. This includes staff training and raising awareness through education and marketing tourism responsibly of sustainability issues among host communities and tourists themselves” (Jenkins, 2013, p.40). Jenkins (2013) argue that there is need to educate tourists towards a niche tourism and ‘tourist test’ for entry at eco-sensitive destinations. The researcher advocates that development and implementation of a specific tourism education policy can bring tourism education closer in line with national tourism policies (Amoah and Baum, 1997). The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and United Nations World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO) has argued that sustainable development have problem solving nature either associated with natural or man-made environment; and takes the benefits to the door step of all the stakeholders (UNEP and UNWTO, 2005). The initiative like ‘tourist test’ can be implemented if it’s a global call otherwise it will bring the economic and environment loss only to the destinations. Hence, there is need to educate national leaders about benefits of tourist test and to make policies accordingly. Tourism, being a ‘multi-industry’ product/service there is need to develop a common set of tourism teaching for all the stakeholders. It is a ‘multi-disciplinary’ there is need to infuse common minimum travel ethics, tourism products, subject alliance, and importance of national tourism among the various discipline pursuers. The COVID-19 effects have endorsed the idea of complete digitalisation of classrooms, global faculty and learners from all across the world at single platform. But tourism is a social phenomenon and personalized services are requisite. Tourism industry demands for ‘actionable knowledge’ than ‘degree certificate’ (Babu, 2017). Academicians are becoming content creators (George, 2017). UNWTO (2018), has given 11 strategies to understand and manage urban tourism. Strategy 10, says “communicate with and engage visitors”, to make it viable, there is a dearth of manpower. Because tourism product comprises of transportation, accommodation, food and beverages as well as ancillary services. To cater only one component of each entity is not a justification of strategy. Therefore, there is again need of tourism education to cater all the component of each entity.

1.13 Threat to Tourism

According to Economic Times (2020), the coronavirus pandemic can hit Indian tourism industry with a loss of rupees 5 lakh crore and job cuts for 4-5 crore

people. Interestingly, UNWTO (2020) has put 'skill development' on agenda to recover tourism from COVID-19 effect. It can be inferred that post COVID-19 tourism industry will demand a new set of skills from the employees. According to the UNWTO (2020), the COVID-19 could lead to an annual decline from 60% to 80% in international tourist arrival as compared to 2019 figures. The Asia Pacific region is worse hit as compared to other UNWTO regions. UNWTO predicted a loss of 100 to 120 million direct jobs across the globe and expected recovery of tourism industry by 2021. The society has been shaken by new world's phenomena "trade war, protectionism, nationalism, climate change, political instability in decisions, use of smart technology (Internet of Things, AI, data mining, machine learning) and new geographical relationships. These phenomena are instable but influencing the tourism immediately. Kerala tourism influenced by Nipah virus (originated in Malaysia in 1998 and that caused the tourism badly in Kerala in 2018 may). According to Lew (2020), the "Global consciousness is needed to give a context and vision for addressing the pressing needs of the world today. It is a platform to integrate sustainability at the individual level, and it justifies the human desire to travel as a consciousness expanding experience. In this way, tourism can serve as a positive force for creating a truly sustainable future world". The tourism and hospitality industry perspective notes that the average age of people seeking employment is increasing, and that more people are in education and training, necessitating tourism operators to follow the same trend when recruiting and investing in human capital. In the new millennium, it is the latter, not capital assets that will make the difference. These not only reflect the potential role tourism education can play within the tourism sector but also points to the enormous task that it ought to pursue in order to produce human resources capable of steering the sector through the present, into the future. It clearly describes the importance of tourism education and training of human resource, even suggests the tourism business houses to understand the importance of the same. It was investigated that tourism education in USA and UK dominated by economic modal while Asian pacific region is not providing in parlance with industry demand (Ayikoru, 2004). "As Youngman (1986) has noted, education is not only inextricably linked to the economic, social and political structure of society, but acts as a setting for class struggles, resistance and opposition to unjust [cultural], socio-political and economic structures. If Youngman is to be believed, then education – in this case tourism higher education - ought to ensure that learners have the opportunity to gain

multiple perspectives on the [tourism] phenomenon they are studying. This way their perceptions of / and actions within the [tourism] world are not limited and/or restricted to the realm of the taken-for-granted issues. With this in mind, the motivation for this study can be traced to two main issues” (p.25).It can be concluded that higher tourism education has the responsibility to enlarge the horizon of students for multiple perspectives. The Covid19 has led to the fracturing of tourism industry all over the world. The countries have imposed the restrictions over visa for tourists. It will define the new age of tourism world. As per the WTTC (2020), an analysis of previous major viral epidemics by experts from WTTC, it takes 19.4 months for recovery in visitor numbers to a destination. It advised that quality of response and management can lower down the recovery time as minimum as 10 months.

1.14 Relevance of this Research

Travel and tourism Industry is a young industry. The tourism world is dynamic and has non-standardization of curriculum. According to Chatzky (2018), job-hopping (less than two years at a position) is key characteristic among the Millennials because it can speed career advancement and more salary. It implies that there are multiples generation at work place and Millennials are not getting work culture in industry. The growth of gig economy because of continuum transformation in technology has led to skilling, upskilling and reskilling of professionals (Ton-Quinlivan, 2018).It can be inferred that new kind of employment skills are needed and there is need for lifelong learning among all the stakeholders of tourism industry. Development in any industry and to make it more beneficial for a country is by and large depends upon the policy frame work by the government of that country. It is deplorable to state that India has neglected this sector for since independence. However, all the developed countries of the world have adopted myriad of ways to reinforce the sector with innovative policies and lifelong learnings. India needs for better planning and tourism research (Seth, 1986) as well as Sofique (2013) recommended the dire need of tourism cadre in the country. India must be the international hub for tourism education and it should be developed for national/regional and international student with wider perspective and qualitative tourism education.

Tourism Education cannot be confined/defined to a particular definition. Tourism Education is a bridge between pristine geographical area and tourism,

creativity and tourism, cultural and its survival for tourism, rigidity of society and tourism, local culture and globalization. Tourism Education is a way to connect natural/artificial resources of this universe with the most curious thought and for the benefits of local/peripheral area of curious thought (visited). Tourism Education should enlighten the individual to observe the surrounding in Action and Reaction approach in sustainable way (mass tourism action and its reaction to the environment, mass tourism can have more economical benefits but what about sustainability of resources). To align the action of tourist with sustainability, we need tourism education. To take tourist beyond city centre, we need motivated tourism professionals (professional must have practical experience, knowledge). These professionals can be produced through quality tourism education only. Even Datar et al. (2017) has advocated curriculum redesign in global context, learning about multi-region management styles, deep cultural understanding (slide-15) and experiential learning (experience and exercise) (slide-14). It was also suggested to practice 360 evaluation and Myers-Briggs type indicators as tool to identify the leadership quality among students (slide-15). According to UNWTO human capital needs for tourism industry in 2020 are not same as of 2030 will be. There will be emergence of new types of tourism commerce, products, services, professions, skills, knowledge and personality attributes. This research work is titled as 'Tourism Education in India: Perception of Academicians and Industry Professionals'. This research has found that tourism academicians and tourism industry professionals feel that there is immediate need for change in curriculum, pedagogy, evaluation of tourism academicians, enrolment proprieties for students from tourism background, need to motivate senior academicians as well as incorporation of Indian Tourism Services for tourism graduates.

The paramount relevance of study is that it finds the numerous gaps and limitations of Indian tourism education system. It suggests ideas as per the findings of research. New dimensions, vision, transformation, quality, efficient human resources, life-long learnings skill, create competence at national and international. It will help to provide a platform in new context i.e. hybrid teaching learning methods, reforms in curriculum development, job creators instead of job seekers, reskilling of academicians, selection of students at the time of hiring, lower down the dropout rate among students, must require skills in tourism industry, ranking of 'subject specific

knowledge' required in tourism industry, relevance of tourism education with regards to sustainable development and tourism graduates in tourism planning.

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